

Design of an Adjustable Warburg Inductor Using an Op-Amp-Based Gyrator and Fractional-Order Capacitor Implementation

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Abstract

Warburg capacitors can be implemented using RC ladder networks, allowing the realization of elements with impedance behavior of the form $Z_c(s)=1/C_\alpha s^{0.5}$. These elements are widely used in modeling diffusion processes in electrochemical systems. On the other hand, gyrator circuits—particularly those based on operational amplifiers—are commonly used to simulate inductors using active components and capacitors. In this study, we propose a method for constructing an adjustable Warburg inductor whose impedance is $Z_L(s)=L_\beta s^{0.5}$ by integrating a Warburg capacitor into an opamp-based gyrator circuit. The resulting system exhibits a fractional-order inductive behavior with tunable parameters, providing a versatile tool for simulating diffusion-controlled inductive elements in analog circuits. Potential applications include bioimpedance modeling, electrochemical systems, and the design of fractional-order filters. Moreover, the circuit can be effectively used as an educational tool in analog electronics or electrochemistry laboratories to demonstrate the behavior of fractional-order elements and active inductor simulations.

Keywords: Fractional-Order Derivative, Ladder Network, Warburg capacitor, Warburg inductor, gyrator circuit, fractional-order circuits, analog circuit simulation, operational amplifier, RC networks, educational circuits.

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1. Introduction

Classical circuit theory relies on integer-order elements like resistors, capacitors, and inductors, defined by first-order time derivatives. However, many real-world systems show memory effects and anomalous behaviors better captured by fractional-order circuit elements (FOCEs), which use non-integer derivatives in their models [1-2]. A fractional-order element is characterized by an impedance of the form $Z(s) = Ks^\alpha$, where s is the complex frequency variable, K is a proportionality constant, and α is a real, non-integer exponent. Depending on the value of α , the fractional element exhibits properties intermediate between resistive, capacitive, and inductive behaviors. Fractional-order models have been applied to systems such as viscoelastic materials, dielectric media, biological tissues, and particularly electrochemical systems, where they offer compact and accurate representations of complex physical processes [3]–[5]. Despite their theoretical appeal, ideal FOCEs are not physically realizable, necessitating approximations over finite frequency ranges. In addition, active circuits, such as those employing operational amplifiers or transconductance amplifiers, have been developed to realize fractional capacitors and inductors with tunable characteristics. Among the most widely used fractional-order elements in practical applications is the Warburg impedance, originally derived from Fick's laws of diffusion to describe the frequency-dependent behavior of ionic transport in electrochemical systems [6]. The (capacitive) Warburg element exhibits an impedance proportional to $s^{-1/2}$, corresponding to a phase angle of -45° , and is commonly used in electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to model mass transport limitations in batteries, fuel cells, and corrosion processes [7]. In modeling terms, the Warburg element serves as a canonical example of a fractional-order system and is often embedded in equivalent circuit models (ECMs) alongside charge-transfer resistances and double-layer capacitances [8]. Realizing Warburg-like behavior in hardware involves either analog approximation through ladder networks or the use of synthetic elements [9]. The synthesis of fractional-order inductors presents additional challenges, especially given the bulk and limitations of traditional inductive components. A promising approach combines ladder network approximations of fractional capacitors with gyrator circuits, which are two-port active devices capable of transforming

capacitive behavior into inductive behavior. By connecting a fractional capacitor emulator to a gyrator, one can effectively realize a fractional-order inductor [10-14]. This method leverages the relative ease of implementing fractional capacitors and expands the design space for FOCEs, particularly in integrated circuit applications. Some articles that discuss or propose RC ladder (or transmission-line/ladder) realizations of Warburg or diffusion-type impedances, and more broadly about equivalent circuits approximating diffusion are given in [15-19]. Several studies have explored the use of RC ladder networks and transmission-line analogs to model diffusion-related impedance behaviors in electrochemical systems. A foundational contribution in this area systematically constructs resistive–capacitive ladder networks and transmission lines to realize a generalized Warburg impedance of the form $A(j\omega)^{-n}$, providing a theoretical basis for approximating fractional-order diffusion behavior through distributed circuit elements [15]. Another study revisits the derivation of the classical Warburg impedance and evaluates the applicability of equivalent circuits—particularly ladder networks and transmission-line models in electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), while also discussing their limitations in accurately capturing diffusion effects [16]. Reduced-order approximations of Warburg-type impedances have been proposed using both ladder and Foster network structures, drawing on classical transmission-line interpretations to achieve computational efficiency and physical relevance [17]. Although originally intended for modeling supercapacitors, one methodology discretizes physical diffusion models into RC networks, effectively approximating diffusion impedance through an analogous ladder-based structure [18]. [19] reviews ladder networks (recurrent RC ladders) in general circuit theory, which underpins understanding of how ladder RC networks behave in frequency domain.

At low frequencies or when large inductance is required, physical inductors become bulky, costly, and prone to parasitic effects [20]. Gyrator circuits using opamps and capacitors offer a compact alternative by emulating inductors [21]. In diffusion-controlled systems—like electrochemical storage devices, biological tissues, and porous materials—traditional elements fall short, and fractional-order models (e.g., Warburg impedance, i.e., $Z_c(s) = 1/C_\alpha s^{0.5}$) better capture their

behavior. RC ladder networks can approximate this response, and when combined with a gyrator, form a fractional inductor with square-root frequency-dependent impedance (with $\alpha=0.5$),

While [22] demonstrates the use of a gyrator with a memristor to create a meminductor emulator for educational and research purposes, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work has reported the use of an opamp-based gyrator circuit combined with a ladder-network-based fractional capacitor to realize an adjustable fractional-order inductor—specifically, a Warburg inductor with square-root frequency dependence. In this study, a tunable Warburg inductor is proposed by integrating an RC-based Warburg capacitor into an opamp-based gyrator circuit. The Warburg capacitor is implemented using an RC ladder network, which, when inserted into the gyrator configuration, produces a synthetic inductor exhibiting fractional-order characteristics ($Z_L(s)=L_\beta s^{0.5}$). By incorporating a potentiometer into the ladder network, the impedance magnitude and effective fractional order can be electronically adjusted, enabling flexible tuning of the inductor’s behavior. This design is particularly well-suited for applications such as fractional-order filters and controllers, where precise impedance shaping is essential. This study presents simulation-based evidence that such a configuration can achieve tunable fractional inductance with acceptable error at high frequencies. Additionally, the circuit serves as a valuable educational tool in analog electronics laboratories, allowing students to explore both active inductor concepts and the behavior of fractional-order circuit elements.

The paper is arranged as follows. In the second section, the constitutive laws of fractional capacitors and inductors are given. A Ladder Network used for obtaining a fractional capacitor is given in the third section. In the fourth section, the Gyrator-based tunable Warburg inductor circuit design is presented, combining an RC-based Warburg capacitor with an opamp-supported gyrator circuit. In the fifth section, the simulation results are given. The paper ends with the conclusion.

2. Fractional Circuit Elements

The constitutive equations of a fractional capacitor is given as

$$i_{C_\alpha}(t) = C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

where $i_{C_\alpha}(t)$, $v_{C_\alpha}(t)$, C_α , and α are the fractional capacitor current, the fractional capacitor voltage, and the fractional capacitor coefficient, and the order of the fractional derivative of fractional capacitor voltage.

The constitutive equations of a fractional inductor is given as

$$v_{L_\beta}(t) = L_\beta \frac{di_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where $i_{L_\beta}(t)$, $v_{L_\beta}(t)$, L_β , and β are the fractional inductor current, the fractional inductor voltage, and the inductor capacitor coefficient, and the order of the fractional derivative of fractional inductor voltage.

Figure 1. The symbols of the fractional inductor and capacitor circuit elements.

Source: Authors.

Their impedances in the Laplace domain is respectively given as

$$Z_C(s) = 1/C_\alpha s^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

and

$$Z_L(s) = L_\beta s^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

3. The Ladder Network for a Fractional Capacitor

A ladder network used to obtain a fractional order capacitor is shown in Figure 1. A finite Warburg impedance can be approximated using such a ladder network composed of resistor-capacitor (R–C) pairs, where each pair is connected in series and the capacitors are shunted to ground (or the return path). When the values of the resistors and capacitors

follow a geometric progression, this topology yields a Warburg-like impedance response over a finite frequency range. The resulting structure effectively emulates the semi-infinite diffusion behavior characteristic of true Warburg elements, making it suitable for modeling fractional-order systems in practical applications.

Figure 2. The R-C ladder.

Source: Authors.

To approximate Warburg behavior over a frequency range ω_{min} to ω_{max} , The parameters of the R-C Ladder can be chosen as follows. Let Number of R-C pairs be n and Time constants are $\tau_k = R_k C_k$, spaced logarithmically and typically chosen as $\tau_k = \tau_0 10^k$ for $k = 0$ to $n-1$. A common method is to keep the time constants spread logarithmically and set:

$$R_k = R_0 a^k, \quad (5)$$

and

$$C_k = C_0 a^{-k} \quad (6)$$

Such that each $\tau_k = R_k C_k$ and equals to a constant.

This gives uniform time constant behavior — important for replicating the $\omega^{-1/2}$ frequency dependence of the Warburg element. In this study, Warburg behavior from 1 Hz to 1000 Hz is approximated by using 3-stage RC ladder, i.e., 3 R-C pairs are chosen and logarithmically spaced: $\tau_1 = 0.001s$, $\tau_2 = 0.01s$, and $\tau_3 = 0.1s$. The values of the resistors and the capacitors which are set as $R_1 = 100 \Omega$, $C_1 = 10 \mu F$, $R_2 = 316 \Omega$, $C_2 = 31.6 \mu F$, $R_3 = 1000 \Omega$, and $C_3 = 100 \mu F$. These values produce time constants of: $\tau = RC \approx 1 \times 10^{-3}$, 1×10^{-2} , and 1×10^{-1} seconds. This covers the frequency range: $f = 1/2\pi\tau$ approximately 1.6 Hz to 160 Hz. For a broader range or smoother fit, the number of stages can be increased.

4. The Gyration-based Warburg Inductor Circuit

Figure 3 illustrates a widely implemented gyrator circuit designed to emulate an inductor. If the resistor C in the gyrator circuit in Figure 4 is replaced with the Ladder-made fractional capacitor C_α , a gyrator circuit behaving as a Warburg inductor or a fractional order inductor can be obtained.

Figure 3. The opamp-based Gyration circuit behaving as an inductor.

Source: Authors.

Figure 4. Gyration circuit behaving as a fractional inductor.

Source: Authors.

Since $R-C_\alpha$ is a series circuit, the node voltage at the noninverting input of the opamp in the Laplace Domain is

$$V^+(s) = V_{in}(s) R / (R + 1/C_\alpha s^\alpha) = V_{in}(s) RC_\alpha s^\alpha / (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha). \quad (7)$$

The current drawn by R_L is:

$$I_{R_L}(s) = (V_{in}(s) - V^+) / R_L \quad (8)$$

$$I_{R_L}(s) = V_{in}(s) / R_L (1 - RC_\alpha s^\alpha / (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha)),$$

$$I_{R_L}(s) = V_{in}(s) / R_L (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha), \quad (9)$$

Then, the impedance seen through R_L is

$$Z_u(s) = R_L (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha), \quad (10)$$

The input impedance of the system depicted in Figure 4 in the Laplace Domain can be expressed as follows:

$$1/Z_{in}(s) = 1/(R + 1/C_\alpha s^\alpha) + 1/Z_u(s), \quad (11)$$

$$1/Z_{in}(s) = 1/(R + 1/C_\alpha s^\alpha) + 1/R_L (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha) \quad (12)$$

$$1/Z_{in}(s) = (C_\alpha s^\alpha + 1/R_L) / (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha). \quad (13)$$

It is found as:

$$Z_{in}(s) = R_L (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha) / (1 + R_L C_\alpha s^\alpha). \quad (14)$$

If $R_L C_\alpha s^\alpha$ is ignored since the value of R_L is low, then, its input impedance is found as

$$Z_{in}(s) \cong R_L (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha) = R_L + R_L RC_\alpha s^\alpha. \quad (15)$$

At high frequencies, the input impedance of the simulated inductor aligns with the desired impedance in parallel with the RC network shown in Figure 4. In conventional gyrator designs, the resistor R is usually chosen to be sufficiently large, ensuring that the dominant impedance term overshadows the RC network's contribution. Also, the series resistance R_L can be ignored at the operation frequencies. As a result, the input impedance of the gyrator circuit depicted in Figure 4 reduces to:

$$Z_{in}(s) \cong R_L RC_\alpha s^\alpha = Z_L(s) = L_\beta s^{0.5}, \quad (16)$$

where $L_\beta = R_L RC_\alpha$.

The frequency-dependent impedance is found as:

$$Z_{in}(j\omega) = R_L RC_\alpha (j\omega)^\alpha, \quad (17)$$

Using Euler identity:

$$(j\omega)^\alpha = (e)^{j\alpha\pi/2} \omega^\alpha = \omega^\alpha (\cos(\alpha\pi/2) + j\sin(\alpha\pi/2)). \quad (18)$$

$$Z_{in}(j\omega) = R_L RC_\alpha \omega^\alpha (\cos(\alpha\pi/2) + j\sin(\alpha\pi/2)). \quad (19)$$

For a Warburg inductor, $\alpha = 0.5$:

$$Z_{in}(j\omega) = R_L RC_\alpha \omega^{0.5} (\cos(\pi/4) + j\sin(\pi/4)) \quad (20)$$

$$Z_L(s) = Z_{in}(j\omega) = L_\beta \omega^{0.5} (\cos(\pi/4) + j\sin(\pi/4)) \quad (21)$$

Eq.s (19)-(21) shows that the input impedance and the input inductance are dependent on the value of the adjustable resistor R . Therefore, a variable fractional order inductor with a series resistor R_L can be done with the ladder network.

If R ranges from R_{min} to R_{max} , the range of L_β is given as follows:

$$R_L R_{min} C_\alpha \leq L_\beta \leq R_L R_{max} C_\alpha. \quad (22)$$

In the phasor domain, a sinusoidal voltage of $v(t) = V_m \cos(\omega t)$ and the input impedance, respectively, turns into:

$$V(j\omega) = V_m, \quad (23)$$

and

$$Z_{in}(s) = \frac{R_L (1 + RC_\alpha (j\omega)^{0.5})}{1 + R_L C_\alpha (j\omega)^{0.5}}. \quad (24)$$

The input current in Laplace domain is calculated as

$$I_{in}(s) = V(s) / Z_{in}(s), \quad (25)$$

$$I_{in}(s) = (1 + R_L C_\alpha s^\alpha) / R_L (1 + RC_\alpha s^\alpha) V(s). \quad (26)$$

The input current in frequency domain is calculated as

$$I_{in}(j\omega) = (1 + R_L C_\alpha (j\omega)^{0.5}) / R_L (1 + RC_\alpha (j\omega)^{0.5}) V_m. \quad (27)$$

The current in time domain can be obtained as

$$i_{in}(t) = \text{Re} \{ I_{in}(j\omega) e^{j\omega t} \}. \quad (28)$$

5. Simulation Results

In this section, the simulation results obtained from MATLAB are provided for values given in Table 1. The input impedances of the Warburg capacitor and the simulated fractional inductor or the gyrator

shown in Figure 5 at high frequencies, i.e., the value of R_L is ignorable at the operating frequency.

The effect of the frequency on the gyrator circuit waveforms are also examined using simulations. The Warburg inductor's impedance is proportional to the square root of frequency and increases with the increasing frequency. This emulator models inductive-like behavior increasing with frequency. At low frequencies, the impedance of the Adjustable Warburg Inductor is low, which indicates that the current will be high—potentially causing the opamp to saturate. A series resistor R_s can be used to limit current at low frequencies to prevent saturation.

Figure 5. Frequency response of **a)** the Ladder network and **b)** the fractional order inductor emulator.

(a)

(b)

Source: Authors.

If the opamp is not saturated and the emulator is under sinusoidal steady-state conditions, assuming a sufficiently high frequency, and the emulator is fed by a sinusoidal voltage of $v(t) = V_m \cos(\omega t)$, the emulator is simulated, and its input current of the emulator is shown in Figure 6.

Table 1. Circuit Parameters used in the simulations.

R_L	1 Ω
R_{min}	5 k Ω
R_{max}	30 k Ω

Source: Authors.

By increasing frequency, the current of the emulator decreases as shown in Figure 6. However, the phase angle of the current remains almost constant at $+45^\circ$. Emulator current is lower than at high frequencies, still leading voltage by $+45^\circ$.

Figure 6. At **(a)** 1 kHz **(b)** 5 kHz **(c)** 10 kHz, the current of the adjustable fractional order capacitor for the sinusoidal voltage of $v(t) = V_m \sin(\omega t)$ where $V_m = 10$ V and $\omega = 20000\pi = 62,831.85$ rad/s.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Source: Authors.

A Warburg inductor's current-voltage hysteresis curve is not the same as an LTI inductor hysteresis curve. However, at high frequencies, the current-voltage hysteresis curve also turns into an ellipse as shown in Figures 7 and 8. The emulator is simulated for five different frequencies and the current-voltage Lissajous curves of the emulator are shown in Figure 7. With increasing frequency, the area of the hysteresis loop decreases since the impedance of the emulator increases and therefore its current decreases. As shown in Figure 7, its hysteresis curve gets broader with decreasing frequency which indicates at low frequencies, the series resistor is dominant.

Figure 7. Lissajous curves of the adjustable fractional order capacitor at three different frequency f values, 1 kHz, 5 kHz and 10 kHz.

Source: Authors.

R allows adjustment of L_β , and this results in a tunable emulator circuit. To demonstrate tunability, the emulator is simulated for three different R values as shown in Figure 8. With increasing R , the area of the hysteresis loop decreases at constant operation frequency since the impedance of the emulator increases and therefore its current decreases.

Figure 8. The Lissajous curves of the adjustable fractional order capacitor obtained for three different R resistance values, 5 k Ω , 10 k Ω , and 30 k Ω at 10 kHz.

Source: Authors.

6. Conclusions

A physical Warburg inductor realized could serve as a foundational element in systems requiring fractional-order impedance, particularly in fractional order controllers and advanced filtering applications. We have demonstrated that a tunable Warburg inductor can be emulated by combining a gyrator circuit with an RC ladder network that models the Warburg capacitor. This approach enables the exploration of fractional-order behavior using standard laboratory components, offering both practical utility and educational value. The emulator's performance has been validated through simulations, suggesting its potential integration into analog front-ends and teaching platforms.

Future work may include extending the emulator to support variable-order dynamics, integrating digital control for real-time tunability, and validating its behavior experimentally in live electrochemical or biomedical systems. Additionally, exploring compact implementations for embedded systems and refining the RC ladder model to better capture non-idealities could further enhance its applicability in both research and industry [23].

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